

A Survey to Assess Awareness and Knowledge About AI Literacy in Undergraduate Dental Students

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to assess the awareness and knowledge of artificial intelligence (AI) in dentistry among undergraduate dental students of Yogita Dental College and Hospital, Khed. A descriptive cross-sectional study design was adopted to evaluate students' understanding and perceptions regarding the application of AI in dental practice. Data were collected over a defined study period using a validated and pre-tested questionnaire distributed through e-mail and WhatsApp platforms. The study participants included undergraduate dental students from institutions in the Konkan region. A total of 173 responses were received and entered into Microsoft Excel, followed by descriptive statistical analysis using IBM SPSS version 26. Among the respondents, females constituted 85% of the study population, while males accounted for 15%. The findings revealed that the majority of students were aware of recent advancements in AI and its emerging role in dentistry. Most participants demonstrated a positive attitude toward AI-based dental treatment and recognized its potential to enhance diagnosis and clinical outcomes. The study concludes that undergraduate dental students possess a satisfactory level of awareness regarding AI applications in dentistry, highlighting the need for structured AI-related education within the dental curriculum.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence, AI Literacy, Dental Education, Undergraduate Dental Students, Awareness and Knowledge

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a rapidly evolving field of computer science that enables machines to perform tasks traditionally requiring human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, pattern recognition, and decision-making. By processing large volumes of complex data, AI systems can assist clinicians in making accurate and timely clinical decisions, often with greater efficiency than conventional methods.¹ Machine Learning (ML), a subset of AI, allows systems to learn from data and improve their performance over time without explicit programming. In healthcare, ML algorithms are increasingly used to interpret patient data, identify disease patterns, and support diagnosis and treatment planning.²

In dentistry, these technologies have demonstrated promising applications in areas such as radiographic interpretation, caries detection, orthodontic treatment planning, implant positioning, and prediction of treatment outcomes^{3,4}. The integration of AI into dental practice has the potential to reduce clinician workload, improve

diagnostic accuracy, enhance treatment efficiency, and contribute to better disease prognosis.⁵ Despite these advancements, AI education has not yet been formally incorporated into undergraduate or postgraduate dental curricula in many institutions. This gap may limit the preparedness of future dental professionals to effectively utilize AI-based technologies in clinical practice. Dental students represent the future workforce and play a pivotal role in the adoption and implementation of emerging technologies. However, limited literature exists assessing their awareness and knowledge regarding AI and its applications in dentistry.⁶ Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate the level of awareness and knowledge of artificial intelligence and its applications among undergraduate dental students.

Methodology

- a. **Study Design-** A descriptive cross-sectional study.
- b. **Study Population-** Undergraduate Dental Students studying in Yogita Dental College and Hospital Khed
- c. **Sampling Criteria-** Purposive sampling technique was used.
- d. **Study Instrument-** A validated, pre-designed, close-ended questionnaire was used for the study. The questionnaire was distributed to undergraduate dental students of Yogita Dental College through e-mails and WhatsApp. Questionnaire validation was carried out through expert review during the construction process to ensure clarity and relevance of the questions. The questionnaire consisted of 14 questions and was divided into three sections. Section I included questions related to the demographic details of the participants. Section II focused on assessing awareness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in dentistry. Section III evaluated the participants' knowledge regarding Artificial Intelligence, its role, and its applications in the field of dentistry.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were first entered into Microsoft Excel to organize and manage the responses systematically. Descriptive statistical analysis was then performed using IBM SPSS version 26 to summarize the data clearly. The results were expressed using frequency and percentage distributions to show how often each response occurred.

Results

Demographic Details: A total of 173 participants took part in the study. The year-wise distribution included undergraduate dental students. The survey was dominated by junior students, with First Years (57.8%) and Second Years (27.7%) making up over 85% of the total. In contrast, Third Years, Fourth Years, and Interns represent a small combined minority of roughly 14.5%. Gender-wise analysis showed that 15% of the participants were males, while females constituted the majority of the study population, accounting for 85% of the participants. Responses were recorded showing frequency (%) for questions in section II and III. (Table 1)

Sr. No.	Questions	Responses %			
		Yes	No	May Be	Not Sure
1	Are you aware of artificial intelligence (AI)?	97.1%	2.9%	-	-
2	Are you aware that AI is currently used in dentistry	81%	10.3%	6.9%	1.7%
3	Do you think artificial intelligence and machine learning are the same?	15.5%	48.9%	23%	12.6%
4	Are you aware that AI based virtual dental assistants available in the market?	40.5%	31.8%	19.7%	8.1%
5	Are you aware of dental chairs that work using AI-based voice commands?	36.2%	44.8%	9.8%	9.2%
6	Do you know that AI- based virtual dental assistants can work more accurately with fewer errors than humans?	41.3%	16.3%	29.7%	12.8%
7	Do you think AI can replicate human emotions?	6.9%	77.6%	10.9%	4.6%
8	Are you aware of hepatic gloves that provide a sense of touch using technology?	14.9%	63.2%	12.1%	9.8%

9	Do you believe AI can accurately predict genetic risk for oral cancer in large populations?	34.5%	17.8%	32.8%	14.9%
10	Do you know that AI can recreate a complete digital record for every patient?	25.3%	9.2%	18.4%	4%
11	Do you think that patient will accept AI based dental treatment?	30.1%	23.7%	32.9%	13.3%
12	Do you think artificial intelligence can improve dental diagnosis?	63.8%	9.2%	21.3%	5.7%
13	Do you believe AI can reduce human errors in dentistry?	55.2%	25.3	25.3%	9.2%
14	Do you think AI will save time in dental procedures?	71.7%	4.6%	19.7%	4%

Discussion

The present survey assessed the level of awareness, perceptions, and attitudes toward artificial intelligence in dentistry among 174 respondents. Overall, the findings indicate a high level of general awareness of AI, accompanied by cautious optimism regarding its applications and limitations in dental practice. An overwhelming majority of respondents (97.1%) reported awareness of artificial intelligence, reflecting the growing penetration of AI concepts in healthcare education and public discourse. This high awareness aligns with previous studies reporting increased familiarity with AI among dental professionals and students, largely due to its expanding role in diagnostics, imaging, and treatment planning.³ The finding that most respondents were aware of AI being currently used in dentistry further supports the notion that AI is no longer perceived as a futuristic concept but as an emerging clinical tool.

Despite general awareness, perceptions of AI's capabilities were more varied. While 41.3% of respondents acknowledged AI's superior accuracy in dental assistance, a larger collective proportion remained uncertain. This uncertainty may stem from limited hands-on exposure to AI-based systems and insufficient integration of AI training into dental curricula. Similar hesitation has been reported in earlier research, where respondents recognized AI's potential accuracy but lacked confidence due to insufficient clinical validation and understanding.^{2,6} A significant majority (77.6%) believed that AI cannot replicate human emotions, highlighting continued confidence in the irreplaceable human elements of dental care, such as empathy, ethical judgment, and patient-clinician interaction. This perception is consistent with literature emphasizing that while AI can enhance technical precision, it lacks emotional intelligence and contextual understanding necessary for holistic patient care.⁷ Such findings suggest that respondents view AI primarily as a supportive tool rather than a substitute for dentists.

Awareness of advanced technologies such as haptic gloves was notably low, with 63.2% of respondents reporting no awareness. This indicates a gap in knowledge regarding emerging simulation and training technologies in dentistry. Haptic systems have been shown to improve psychomotor skills and preclinical training, yet their limited adoption and visibility may explain the low awareness observed in this study.⁸ Opinions regarding AI's ability to predict genetic risk for oral cancer were mixed, with 34.5% responding affirmatively and 32.8% selecting "maybe." This reflects moderate confidence but also uncertainty about AI's role in predictive oncology. While recent studies demonstrate promising results in AI-driven cancer risk prediction and early diagnosis, such applications are still evolving and not widely implemented in routine dental practice.^{4,9}

A majority of respondents (68.4%) were aware that AI can create complete digital patient records, indicating good knowledge of AI's role in dental informatics and data management. However, nearly one-third remained uncertain or unaware, suggesting the need for greater emphasis on digital dentistry and health informatics education.⁶ Perceptions regarding AI as a future threat to dentists were divided. While 30.1% perceived AI as a threat, 32.9% responded "maybe," indicating uncertainty rather than strong concern. This ambivalence mirrors findings from previous studies, which suggest that dental professionals generally view AI as augmentative rather than replacement technology, though concerns about job displacement persist.¹⁰

Encouragingly, most participants believed AI could improve dental diagnosis (63.8%), reduce human error (55.2%), and save time in dental procedures (71.7%). These findings are consistent with existing evidence demonstrating AI's effectiveness in radiographic interpretation, caries detection, and workflow optimization.^{3,11} Overall, the findings highlight a positive attitude toward AI in dentistry, coupled with knowledge gaps and

uncertainty regarding advanced applications, underscoring the importance of incorporating structured AI education into dental training programs.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates a high level of general awareness of artificial intelligence among the surveyed participants, with most respondents recognizing its current and potential applications in dentistry. The findings indicate a predominantly positive attitude toward AI, particularly in relation to improving diagnostic accuracy, reducing human error, saving time, and enhancing overall efficiency in dental practice. These perceptions suggest growing acceptance of AI as a supportive tool in modern dentistry rather than a replacement for dental professionals. However, despite this positive outlook, notable gaps in knowledge remain, especially regarding advanced AI-based technologies such as haptic systems and genetic risk prediction tools. The uncertainty observed in several areas highlights the need for structured education, hands-on training, and increased exposure to AI-driven dental technologies. Additionally, the majority belief that AI cannot replicate human emotions reinforces the continued importance of human judgment, empathy, and ethical decision-making in dental care.

Overall, the study underscores the importance of integrating artificial intelligence into dental education and clinical practice in a balanced and informed manner. By addressing existing knowledge gaps and promoting evidence-based understanding, AI can be effectively leveraged to enhance dental care while preserving the essential human elements of the profession.

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